

AYURVEDIC APPROACH TO *EK KUSTHA* (PSORIASIS): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Ek kustha, a kind of *Kshudra Kustha*, is caused by an imbalance of *Vata* and *Kapha* doshas and has clinical signs similar to psoriasis. Psoriasis is an autoimmune and chronic inflammatory skin illness with erythematous, clearly delineated papules and spherical plaques coated in silvery micaceous scale. It primarily affects the skin of the elbows, gluteal cleft, knees, trunk and scalp. Psoriasis can cause psychological suffering, including sadness and social isolation, and has been linked to increased suicidal ideation rates. The primary treatments for psoriasis include steroid creams, vitamin D3 cream, PUVA, and immune system suppressing drugs like methotrexate. Long-term usage of these contemporary treatments can lead to serious consequences. There is a need for treatment that is both effective and safe. This case study focused on Psoriasis as *Ekkustha*, and Ayurvedic treatment was devised accordingly. *Shodhana* (*Vaman karma* & *Virechana karma*) and *Shamana chikitsa* (internal herbo-mineral preparations and external oil application) both produced significant outcomes.

KEYWORDS: *Ek kustha*, *Kshudra Kustha*, Psoriasis, *Vaman*, *Virechana*.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic, immune-mediated inflammatory condition that primarily affects the skin and joints. In India, its prevalence ranges from approximately 0.44% to 2.8%. Males are affected nearly twice as often as females.^[1] The condition can involve various body sites, including the scalp, face, trunk, limbs, palms, and soles. Diagnosis is typically based on tissue

biopsy and the distribution pattern of skin lesions. Several clinical types of psoriasis have been identified, including Plaque Psoriasis (Psoriasis Vulgaris), Inverse Psoriasis, Guttate Psoriasis, Pustular Psoriasis, and Erythrodermic Psoriasis.^[2] Due to its chronicity, recurrent nature, and visible symptoms, psoriasis significantly impacts patients' psychological well-being and social functioning, often resulting in psychosocial disability that hinders daily activities and interpersonal interactions.

In Ayurveda, skin disorders are generally categorized under the term *Kushtha*. Many Ayurvedic formulations described under *Kushtha Chikitsa* have been effectively used by practitioners to manage various skin conditions. alongside *Kushtha Chikitsa*. In the present case, this integrative Ayurvedic approach led to early recovery from psoriatic lesions, with no recurrence observed to date. *Ek-kushtha* is one of the skin disorders explained by *Acharya* in *kushtha-chikitsa adhyaya*. There are two types of *kushtha*, namely *mahakushtha* and *kshudrakushtha*. *Ek-kushtha* is one of *kshudra-kushtha*. *Aswedanam* (not perspire), *mahavastu* (extensive) and *yana-masyoshakalopamam* (looks like fish scale), *arun varna* (discoloration) are the main symptoms *ek-kushtha*.^[3] *Ek-kushtha* is most closely resembles like Psoriasis. Psoriasis is a long-lasting autoimmune disease characterized by patches of abnormal skin. These skin patches are typically red, dry, itchy, and scaly. Psoriasis varies in severity from small, localized patches to complete body coverage.

In the modern era, various forms of pollution, unhealthy diets, and the use of numerous cosmetics and chemicals contribute to the increasing prevalence of skin diseases. In India, the prevalence rate of psoriasis ranges from 0.44% to 2.8%. Ayurvedic treatment for psoriasis involves two primary approaches: *Shodhan* and *Shaman chikitsa*. *Shodhan chikitsa* includes treatments such as *Vaman* (emesis) and *Virechana* (purgation), along with *Raktamokshana* (blood-letting). These treatments are administered based on the dominance of doshas: *Ghrita* is recommended when *Vata* is prevalent, *Vamana Karma* for *Kapha* dominance, and *Virechana Karma* or *Raktamokshana* for *Pitta* dominance.^[4] On the other hand, *Shaman chikitsa* utilizes both internal and external medications. The medicines used in this approach typically possess *tikta* (bitter) and *katu* (pungent) properties, aimed at purifying the *Vata*, *Kapha*, and *Rakta doshas*. *Ek-kushtha* can be effectively treated through *panchakarma* procedures combined with appropriate internal medications, leading to significant improvements in patient outcomes.

CASE REPORT

A 22-year- male student came at *Panchkarma* OPD of *Sanjeevni Chikitsshalya* Jodhpur presented with chief complaint of erythematous patches, scaling present in scalp region and abdomen region, pain, and roughness of skin over the whole of trunk and the upper limbs since 5-6 month.

Present History

Patient was well before 5-6 month. But since then patient has been suffering from erythematous patches, scaling present in scalp region and abdomen region, pain and roughness of skin over the whole of trunk and the upper limbs. The patient took allopathy medications for above complaints, but there was no any satisfactory relief, so he came to *Sanjeevni Chikitsshalya* for further treatment.

Personal history

- Appetite – Poor
- Bowel – Constipation
- Sleep – Sound Sleep
- Food habits - Habit of eating guru *ahara* (heavy) like curd, *snigdha* (oily) foods, sour and salty foods.

Past history

No any family history was present regarding psoriasis or any dermatological disorders. No any history of hypertension, diabetes and bronchial asthma. No any history of surgery.

Astavidha Pariksha

- *Nadi* (pulse) - 78/min.
- *Mala* (stool) – Constipated
- *Mutra* (urine) - 3-4 times in a day
- *Jeeva* (tongue) -*Pakrut*
- *Agni* -*Mand*
- *Shabda* (speech) - Normal.
- *Akruti* - *Madhyama*.
- *Bala* - *Madhyama*.
- B.P - 120/70 mm/Hg.

Examination of Skin

- A. Inspection** – Patches - Reddish erythematous graze over Whole Abdomen and Dorsal aspect of trunk. - Color – Red.
- B. Palpation** – Moisture - Dryness - Temperature – Warmth to touch - Texture – Rough.

Laboratory Investigations

Routine blood tests were within normal limits, including CBC with ESR, LFT, RFT, RBS, CRP.

Treatment Plan

Table no. 1: Shodhan chikitsa - by following the purvakarma, pradhankarma and pschyat karma.

DATE	MEDICINE	DOSE	ROUTE	DURATION
18 April 2025	<i>Deepan</i> (Appetizers) – <i>pachan</i> (Carminatives) with <i>Trikatu Churna</i>	5 gm Twice a day before meal with lukewarm water	Oral	1 days
19 April 2025 to 21 April 2025	<i>Abhyantar Snehapana</i> (Internal administration) with <i>Go ghrita</i>	30 ml – 1 st day 60 ml – 2 nd day 90 ml- 3 rd day (Empty stomach at morning time with lukewarm water)	Oral	3 days
22 April 2025	<i>Sarvanga abhyanga</i> followed by <i>sarvang swedan</i> ^[5]	<i>Psoria</i> oil Followed by <i>Bashpaswed</i>	External application	1 days
23 April 2025	<i>Vamana</i> (Followed by <i>sansarjan karma</i> for 5 days)	<i>Madhanphaladi yoga</i>	Oral	For 1 day at morning time after <i>snehan</i> and <i>swedan</i>
Virechan Karma				
1 May 2025 to 3 May 2025	<i>Abhyantar Snehapana</i> (Internal administration) with <i>Mahatikta ghrita</i>	30 ml – 1 st day 60 ml – 2 nd day 90 ml - 3 rd day (Empty stomach at morning time with lukewarm water)	Oral	3 days
4 May 2025 to 6 May 2025	<i>Sarvanga abhyanga</i> followed by <i>sarvang swedan</i>	<i>Psoria</i> oil Followed by <i>Bashpaswed</i>	External application	3 Days

7 May 2025	Virechan Karma (Followed by sansarjan karma for 5 days)	Trivrut Avaleha 100 gm	Oral	1 Day
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Paschyat Karma - After getting *Samyaka Vamana Lakshana*, *Dhoomapan* was given with stick made of *Panchkol* (which is made from *Panchkol churna* paste apply over cotton and make a stick of it, dried it) for 5 minutes by each nostril. Then patient was advised to follow the *Sansarjana Karma* for 5 days. *Sansarjana Karma*^[6] was given in the form of *Peya*, *Vilepi*, *Akrita Mudga Yusha*, *Krita Mudga Yusha* for 5 days.

Table no. 2: Shaman Aushadhi (Pallitative Medication).

Medicine	Dose	Anupan	Route of administration	Time	Duration
1. <i>Avipatkar Churna</i> <i>Giloya churna</i> <i>Gandhak Rasayan</i> <i>Chopchini churna</i> <i>Shankh Bhasma</i>	3 gm 1 gm 250 mg 2 gm 250 mg	Luke warm water	Oral	BD (Empty stomach)	2 month
2. <i>Kaishore Guggulu</i>	2-2 tab	Luke warm water	Oral	BD (Empty stomach)	2 month
3. <i>Arogyavidhini vati</i>	2-2 tab	Luke warm water	Oral	BD (Empty stomach)	2 month
4. <i>Syrup khoon safa</i>	10 ml	Luke warm water	Oral	BD (After food)	2 month
5. <i>Triphala churna</i>	5 gm	Luke warm water	Oral	HS	2 month
6. 777 Oil <i>Karanj Oil</i>	Quantity Sufficient After bath		External Application	Twice a day	2 month

Grading – PASI (Psoriasis Area Severity Index) Score^[7]

Within each area, the severity is estimated by three clinical sings: Severity parameters are measured on the scale of 0 to 4, from none to maximum. The body is divided into four sections [head (H) (10 % of a person's skin); arms (A) (20%); trunk (T) (30%); legs (L) (40%)]. Each of this area is scored by itself, and then the four scores are combined into the final PASI. For each section, the percent of area of skin involved, is estimated and then transformed into a grade from 0 to 6.

Table no. 3: Extent of body region affected.

Percentage of body region affected	Extend indicator
No involved area	Grade: 0
<10% of involved area	Grade: 1
10- 30% of involved area	Grade: 2
30 – 50% of involved area	Grade: 3
50 – 70% of involved area	Grade: 4
70 – 90% of involved area	Grade: 5
90 – 100% of involved area	Grade: 6

Table no. 4: Showing assessment criteria of 2 months of treatment.

Head and Trunk			
	Before treatment	First follow up	Second follow up
Skin area involved	3	2(only trunk, front)	0
Redness	4	3	0
Thickness	3	2	0
Scaling	3	2	0
Total PASI Score	13	9	0

Table no. 5: Showing Overall result of treatment.

	Before treatment	First follow up	Second follow up
Area involved	30-50 %	10-30 %	0%
Redness	Severe	Mild	Absent
Thickness	Moderate	Mild	Absent
Scaling	Severe	Mild	Absent

OBSERVATION

Before

Before

After

After

Picture no. 1: Showing before and after *vaman* and *virechan* therapy.

After 30 days

After 60 days

Picture no. 2: Showing after *saman chikitsa* at 30th days and 60th days.

DISCUSSION

The disease is categorized under *Raktapradoshaj Vyadhi* (arising from vitiated Rakta), with *Vata-Kapha* predominance and involvement of all three *doshas* (Tridoshaj). Both *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* are recommended in the Samhitas for the management of *Kushtha*.^[8] In the present case, the patient was treated with these modalities. As *Purva Karma*, *Deepana-Pachana* with *Trikatu Churna* was administered to enhance digestion (*Agnivardhaka*) and digest Ama. This was followed by *Snehapana* with *Go Ghrita* for three days, which helped pacify *Vata dosha*. For *Abhyanga*, Psoria oil was used to reduce dryness, moisturize the skin, improve circulation, and relieve itching. Thereafter, *Sarvanga Swedana* was performed, which facilitated *Dosha Vilayana* (liquefaction of doshas), mobilizing them from the *Shakha*

(tissues) to the *Koshtha* (viscera) for elimination. It also helped in clearing *Srotorodha* (obstruction in channels).

Action of *Snehapana*

Go ghrta The ingredients of *Go ghrta* are *Madhur Rasatmaka*, *Snigdha* and *ushna guna*, *Madhur Vipaki* and *Ushna Viryatmaka* It predominantly acts on *Kleda*, *Meda*, *Lasika*, *Rakta*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*, thereby supporting the restoration of balance in vitiated *Doshas* and *Dhatus*. It exhibits properties such as *Raktashodhaka* (blood purifying), *Kushtaghna* (beneficial in skin disorders), *Kandughna* (relieving itching), and *Varnya* (enhancing complexion).^[9] *Ghrta* (ghee), owing to its lipophilic nature, serves as an excellent carrier, enabling active principles to reach target organs by penetrating up to the cellular level, including mitochondria and the nuclear membrane. Moreover, it helps preserve the natural texture and integrity of the skin.^[10]

Action of *Abhyanga* with *Psoria tail*

For the purpose of *Abhyanga* or *Bahyasnehana* (External oleation) the *Psoria tail* is used. The most of *Dravyas* of *Psoria tail* are have It possesses *Katu*, *Tikta*, and *Kashaya rasa* along with *Ushna virya*, which help in pacifying *Kapha* and *Vata dosha*. Its *Snigdha guna* counteracts *Rukshata*, *Kharata*, and *Parushata*. Additionally, it exhibits *Raktashodhaka*, *Kushtaghna*, and *Kandughna* properties. The *Sukshmagamitva* nature of the oil facilitates penetration into subtle channels, ensuring effective absorption. The *Kashaya rasa* of the ingredients aids in reducing *Kleda*.^[11] Moreover, *Psoria tail* possesses antiseptic, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory actions. The *Psoria tail* is effective in the Symptoms of *Eka Kushtha* due to these properties.

Action of *Vaman karma*

The *Prakupit doshas* (*Vitiated dosha*), primarily *Pitta* and *Kapha*, are eliminated from the *Koshtha* by *Vaman*. With qualities like *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, *Vyavayi*, and *Vikasi*, the *Vamanopaga* medications (which aid in emesis) like *Madanphal Churna*, *Vacha Churna*, *Pippali Churna*, *Saindhav*, *Madhu*, and *Yashtimadhu Phanta* improve the rate of absorption and aid in reaching the heart. It travels to all *Shukshma* and *Sihool Strotas* from *Hriday* to the *Dhamani* (Artery). It cleanses the body of all toxins. There is *Agni* and *Vayu Mahabhutas* predominance. *Urdhwabhagahar Prabhav* of *Vamak Dravyas* which causes the eradication of *Doshas* from the upward route. This therapy is particularly helpful for the eradication of exacerbated *Doshas*.^[12]

Action of Virechan karma

Virechan medication brings out the therapeutic purgation due to its *Prabhava* (potency). These medications can aid in the induction of purgation because they have a natural inclination to go downhill due to the dominance of *Jala and Prithvi Mahabhuta*. The waste products can be brought into the intestine to maintain homogeneity from where they can be eliminated out of the body by the action of the intestine, which is induced by the *Virechana* drug, as has already been mentioned. This process can occur wherever the waste products are present in the body, whether they are extracellular, intracellular, or in plasma. The supplied medication's active ingredients will activate the mucosal membrane and momentarily alter the normal permeability of the mucosal lining, causing morbid pollutants that were transported from the cellular to the gut levels via *Snehana and Swedana Karma* to exude through the anal pathway.

Gandhak Rasayan

It acts as *Kushtaghna, Kandughna, Dahaprashaman, Raktashodhak, Vranaropak, Twachya and Krumighna*. It is mainly indicated in *Kushtaroga*. It possess the property like antibacterial, antiviral and antimicrobial.^[13] It reduces the itching and infection.

Kaishore Guggulu

It balances *Pitta and Kapha*, particularly when it affects musculoskeletal system. Its main ingredients—*Guduchi, Triphala and Trikatu*—when combined with *Guggulu*, create a detoxifying and rejuvenating combination aimed primarily at removing deep-seated *Pitta* from the tissues.

Arogyavardhini vati

It is a useful formulation in treating skin diseases like eczema, excessive dryness of skin, rashes etc. It is indicated in various skin diseases due to vitiated *Vat and Kapha*. *Ekakushtha* is disease of *Vata-kapha dushti*, so it is useful in *Eka kushtha* (psoriasis).

Khoon Safa

Khoon Safa is believed to purify the blood by eliminating toxins and supporting the liver. It Reducing Inflammation: Some ingredients in *Khoon Safa*, like neem, have anti-inflammatory properties that may help reduce the inflammation associated with psoria. *Khoon Safa* is also thought to balance the doshas (vital energies) in the body, potentially contributing to a more harmonious internal environment that could benefit psoria. By supporting the immune

system, *Khoon Safa* might help the body better manage the immune dysregulation that plays a role in psoria.

777 oil

It contain *Wrightia tinctoria* and coconut oil, effectively treats psoriasis by Reducing excessive skin cell growth, Alleviating inflammation, Moisturizing and reducing itching, Enhancing absorption of active ingredients and Extending skin cell lifespan.

Karanj oil

It is known for its strong antimicrobial properties. It's often used to treat skin conditions like eczema, psoriasis, scabies, and fungal infections. Its Anti-inflammatory soothing properties help reduce inflammation and relieve itching or irritation.

CONCLUSION

Eka Kushtha which is a type of *Kshudra Kushtha* can be correlated to Psoriasis. From the above case, we can draw a conclusion that trunk psoriasis can be successfully managed through Ayurvedic treatment modalities like repeated *Shodhana and Shamana*. As Ayurvedic treatment helps to relieve symptoms of disease and an attempt to provide safe and effective treatment to the patient. From the above case it can be concluded that the *Eka Kushtha* can be successfully treated with the *Shodhan and Shaman Chikitsa*.

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